

From Robotic to IoT Systems: Exploring the Reuse of a Robotic Orchestration DSL in the IoT domain

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Abstract

Low-code approaches are gaining traction in the development of robotic systems due to their support for rapid iteration and involvement from domain experts. These approaches simplify the definition of mission logic, allowing it to be composed, verified, and deployed through domain-specific abstractions. In this context, we present how our low-code DSL, originally designed for robotic orchestration, can be repurposed for IoT systems. By redefining only the domain abstractions, we preserve the DSL syntax, semantics, and verification workflow. Two examples, a smart-building policy and an inspection cell, illustrate how the same constructs that coordinate robotic behaviors can express IoT interactions through MQTT adapters. Although these initial experiments are small, they suggest that the architectural and verification principles developed for autonomous robots can be generalized to IoT systems. The paper aims to initiate a discussion on the potential benefits of a unified, verifiable low-code framework that spans both domains.

CCS Concepts

• **Computer systems organization** → **Embedded and cyber-physical systems**; • **Software and its engineering** → **Domain specific languages**; *Source code generation*.

Keywords

low-code, IoT, verification, visual programming

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1 Introduction

Since the advent of Industry 4.0, there is a growing interest in the development of Internet of Things (IoT) applications. Today, things such as smart homes and automation systems are increasingly prevalent, if not already mainstream. IoT applications enable end users to remotely control home devices from their smartphones and automate everyday tasks. Building robust IoT systems involves

integrating devices, services, and data pipelines across constrained networks and heterogeneous platforms. In practice, orchestration logic is often implemented as ad hoc scripts or workflow patches that entangle domain behavior with protocols and deployment particulars (edge containers, cloud functions) [2]. As a result, failures such as inconsistent device states, conflicting actuations, or unhandled exceptions are common sources of system fragility [7].

In the quest to facilitate the development of these “smart” things, there is a growing interest in visual programming languages [2]. Visual programming enables users to develop programs by dragging and dropping graphical elements. This paradigm greatly reduces the barriers to complex programming tasks that use text-based computer code. Thus, even users unfamiliar with programming can write programs. While not the only one, visual programming is a core tenet of low-code approaches. Low-code development is a technology that facilitates the rapid development, configuration, and deployment of applications with minimal or almost no coding, as opposed to traditional text-based programming. This technology is increasingly being adopted in domains that require rapid iteration and domain expert involvement.

While interesting in the context of IoT, the quest to facilitate the development of correct programs is shared across several domains of computer science. In recent work on autonomous robotics, we introduced KODA, a mission-oriented low-code Domain-Specific Language (DSL) that enables domain experts to compose behaviors declaratively through sequencing, repetition, and event-driven constructs [13]. These missions are automatically translated into Dezyne [3], allowing formal verification of control-flow soundness and contract conformance.

This work builds upon prior KODA research and proposes applying the same language to IoT systems without modifying its syntax or verification pipeline. Instead, we redefine the capability library to target IoT devices and protocols. The core language constructs, reference architecture, and verification process are inherited unchanged from prior KODA work. The contributions of this paper lie in:

- Adapting KODA’s foundation to the IoT domain.
- Including an IoT-oriented capability library and protocol-aware wrapper generation.
- An explicit mapping between IoT concepts and the existing orchestration and verification model.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents related work, while Section 3 provides an overview of the existing approach. Section 4 explains how the key concepts translate between robotics and IoT. Section 5 presents two small examples

of the approach in a simulated scenario. Finally, Section 6 discusses the results and implications of the approach and concludes.

2 Related work

Low-code and model-driven approaches have been increasingly applied to IoT systems to manage complexity and heterogeneity [6, 11]. Existing tools, such as Node-RED and ThingML [4], enable the visual composition of IoT behaviors but offer limited guarantees regarding correctness or runtime safety. More formalized approaches, such as ECHO [10] and Cloud4IoT [9], address deployment and interoperability but do not provide explicit behavioral verification. Recent studies on formal methods for IoT [1, 8] demonstrate how model checking and temporal logic can detect design faults; however, they often require specialized modeling languages that are inaccessible to domain experts.

This work does not aim to replace current IoT low-code environments but to complement them by addressing existing behavioral orchestration concerns. The aforementioned low-code environments are primarily expressive for event-driven integration, where system behavior emerges from message routing between components. While effective for data-centric workflows, control flow, concurrency, and cancellation are typically encoded implicitly through wiring conventions or shared state. In contrast, KODA adopts behavior and capability orchestration as first-class abstractions, allowing sequencing, parallel execution, and abort semantics to be expressed explicitly and compositionally. This explicit behavioral representation preserves intent at the model level and enables formal verification of IoT orchestration logic, which is difficult to achieve in generic flow-based environments [4].

3 Approach overview

We begin by summarizing our verification-aware low-code workflow and the roles of each artifact: the Reference Architecture (RA), the structural and behavioral visual DSLs, automated verification, and code generation. The workflow is illustrated in Figure 1.

In the proposed low-code approach, a domain expert—someone who understands what the robot should accomplish but not how to implement it—uses our Low-Code Development Platform (LCDP) to describe a task, such as a factory pick-and-place. Guided by a RA that defines the available capabilities and their interfaces, the expert first composes the system’s structure by selecting the necessary capabilities (e.g., *Inspect*, *Grip*). Next, they describe the system’s behavior by specifying strategies in which these capabilities interact to achieve the goal, without worrying about the underlying middleware or control logic. The platform then formalizes this composition by translating the models into verifiable Dezyne specifications, which are automatically checked for safety, liveness, and contract satisfaction. Detected inconsistencies are reported to the user for correction. Once verified, the models are transformed into executable code that preserves the verified logic and can be deployed directly to the system.

To facilitate development and maintain a modular approach, the visual languages are kept separate from the Dezyne generation. Underlying the LCDP is KODA, a DSL responsible for describing the different capabilities and translating comprehensible flows into formal Dezyne models. The visual languages with which the domain experts interact are a different representation on top of KODA.

Figure 1: Verification-aware low-code workflow based on Reference Architecture (RA)

3.1 Reference Architecture

The RA defines reusable capability interfaces and fault policies that standardize interactions between components. The RA breaks down the typical three-layer low-code architecture into five key functionalities of the robotics domain, which we argue also apply to IoT systems: **Planning**, **World Model**, **Control**, **Actuation**, and **Perception** [13]. For the IoT variant, the same RA is reused, and only the concrete capability implementations differ; sensors, actuators, and services are now mapped to networked endpoints, rather than robot drivers.

3.2 Verification with Dezyne

For the formal verification of the defined models, the approach relies on Dezyne [3]. Dezyne is a design-by-contract language and adopts a message-passing programming model [5], in which messages are first-class in the syntax, and a process-algebraic interpretation provides the semantics. This interpretation enables reasoning about equivalences, which in turn is used in verification, allowing compositions to retain their individually verified properties. In particular, Dezyne automatically verifies the following properties: **Deadlock**, **Unreachable code**, **Unhandled events**, and **Livelock** [3, 13]. Moreover, it supports the modeling of unstable networks, but it cannot verify timing properties.

4 KODA: From robotics to IoT

IoT systems share many structural and behavioral patterns with the robotic domain: sensors emit signals, actuators execute commands, and services provide contextual information or decision logic. With this idea, Table 1 describes the core semantic concepts of our approach and how they map to IoT. Table 2 presents the constructs used in KODA to model the different robotic strategies.

Given the description of these concepts and constructs, we argue that the same approach discussed in Section 3 can be applied to

Table 1: Core semantic concepts in the IoT context

Concept	Robotics	IoT
Task	Goal to be achieved.	Behavioral scope for devices or services.
Capability	Unit of robot behavior.	Device or service operation.
Strategy	Control logic combining capabilities.	Orchestration of device and service actions.
Signal	Sensor or perception event.	Device event (e.g., state change).
Trigger	Deterministic actuation command.	Networked command or service call.
Error	Capability failure.	Device failure.
Abort	Controlled stop or safety preemption.	User cancel or policy override.
Contract	Preconditions, effects, and hazards.	Preconditions, effects, and policies.

Table 2: Key language constructs for behavior modeling

Construct	DSL semantics
Sync calls	Blocking calls with reply before proceeding.
Async calls	Non-blocking calls with later confirmation.
Sequential	Execute tasks in order, each with clear termination.
Parallel	Run tasks concurrently; join on completion.
Handler	Transition triggered by event arrival.
Repeat	Re-execute behavior until stopped.
Every	Execute behavior periodically.
Within	Execute task within a fixed amount of time.

IoT systems. All syntactic constructs, event semantics, and verification artifacts remain unmodified. Since the DSL semantics and verification backend are maintained, the compiler continues to generate Dezyne models that can be verified for the same properties as those used in robotics. This demonstrates that verifiability can be preserved across domains through consistent abstractions, rather than new formal methods.

4.1 Wrapper and Adapter Generation

While the architectural and verification workflow remain unchanged, the main difference from the robotic version of the approach lies in the generation stage. Instead of producing Robot Operating System (ROS) 2 nodes, the compiler is modified to generate MQTT clients and servers that wrap the verified models and handle network communication.

Each capability interface declares its interaction pattern as either *synchronous (sync)* or *asynchronous (async)*, which determines how the generated wrapper behaves. Synchronous bindings represent blocking interactions, where the client waits for a reply before continuing. Asynchronous bindings represent fire-and-forget calls that return immediately, with the outcome reported later through an event. These two interaction classes are preserved exactly as in the robotic version of the language, ensuring that verification results remain valid regardless of the target runtime.

At generation time, the compiler interprets the capability signature and produces a lightweight C++ wrapper for each operation.

For IoT targets, these wrappers are configured using message templates that define the structure of MQTT messages. Templates are specified directly in the capability declaration, as shown in Listing 1.

```

1 // IoT
2 async "ventilation" "{ \"cmd:\" \"${1}\" }" { ... }
3 // Robotics
4 async "/handler/action" "std_msgs::String" { ... }

```

Listing 1: Capability modification example

Here, "ventilation" defines the MQTT topic and "{"cmd": "\${1}" the message payload format, where \$1 is replaced by the actual argument at runtime. This mechanism enables message structures to be changed without altering the verified logic of the system. The underlying Dezyne model and generated C++ verification stubs remain identical; thus, a call in the robotic system and a call in the IoT system share the same semantics and verification coverage, even though each compiles to a different middleware. This separation of concerns allows the same language and verification pipeline to serve both domains while supporting flexible deployment targets.

5 Evaluation: Two Scenarios

We evaluate the approach on two realistic but concise scenarios. Artifacts and scripts are provided as supplementary material [12]. In both scenarios, we use Mosquitto to broker messages, and a Python script to connect to the necessary MQTT topics and simulate reactions to various devices and services.

5.1 S1: Smart-Building Policy

For the first scenario, we have a typical smart building setup. The goal is to maintain air quality and manage lighting in open-plan zones. The task polls the devices every few milliseconds and updates the services accordingly. Once a person is detected in the room, the lights turn on; they turn off once the room is empty. Moreover, while there are people in the room, the ventilation system is responsible for addressing air quality issues within a five-minute time frame.

5.2 S2: Inspection cell

In the second scenario, we have a pick-and-place cell equipped with a conveyor belt, a robotic arm, a camera, and a ticketing system to notify of any failures. The cell begins by activating its inspection camera and conveyor. The conveyor runs until an invalid part is detected; then, a failure ticket is created, and the robot arm is sent to place the part in the rejected bin. Listing 2 presents the specified behavior for this scenario textually in KODA.

```

1 strategy {
2   abrt: conveyor.stop() --> image.stop() -->
3     arm.stop() --> end;
4   reject: ( arm("reject_loc")
5     on error abrt
6     on abort abrt ) --> ticket.create();
7   detected: conveyor.stop() -->
8     ( arm("pick_loc")
9     on error abrt on abort abrt ) --> reject;
10  main: repeat( image.start() -->
11    ( conveyor()
12      on error abrt on abort abrt
13      on image.invalid() detected ));
14 }

```

Listing 2: The inspection scenario expressed in KODA

5.3 Verification evaluation

To assess the model verification, intentional mistakes are introduced into the behaviors. These represent typical errors made in IoT development that the proposed approach aims to tackle. To ensure independent verification, the mistakes are introduced separately: (1) missing abort handlers, (2) missing error handlers, and (3) missing terminators (end). Besides these, runtime failures are triggered in the simulator during runtime to verify that these cases are correctly handled.

Figure 2 presents an example of a generated counterexample for S1. The different Dezyne *components* are shown in yellow while the task behavior is shown in green. Some of the components of the system were intentionally omitted to improve readability. The sequence illustrates the sequence of triggers and signals that lead to the invalid situation, specifically the absence of an abort handler in the strategy.

Figure 2: Example of a generated counter-example for S1.

5.4 Results

In the smart-building policy (S1), KODA expresses a continuous, event-driven control loop that monitors occupancy and air quality while coordinating lighting and ventilation systems. Verification ensures that all possible errors and abort paths lead to a safe state, i.e., no device remains active after an abort. The inspection cell (S2) extends this principle to a more industrial setting, mirroring a robotic pick-and-place workflow. Here, verification checks that error propagation is complete and that components are stopped. Table 3 presents a summary of the scenarios' metrics for reference.

Table 3: Case study statistics

Scenario	States	Transitions	Verif. time
S1	4	31	16s
S2	4	18	12s

Both scenarios confirm that the same mission-oriented abstractions used in robotic orchestration can be applied directly to IoT environments. In both cases, the task structure and strategy semantics remained unchanged, while only the capability definitions and adapters differed. Verification detected missing handlers and incomplete terminations as expected, confirming that correctness checks operate independently of the runtime backend. These results indicate that the proposed language can represent asynchronous, concurrent IoT interactions while maintaining the same compositional and verifiable structure as in the robotic domain.

6 Conclusion

This paper explored the reuse of a mission-oriented orchestration DSL originally developed for robotics in the context of IoT systems. By adapting only the generation backend to produce MQTT-based wrappers, the same syntax, semantics, and verification workflow were retained. The evaluation on two compact scenarios showed that verification outcomes and behavioral semantics remain consistent across domains, supporting the feasibility of the approach.

Future work will extend evaluation to larger hybrid robotic-IoT environments, expand timing and scheduling primitives to capture real-time dependencies, and enrich capability contracts with explicit delivery semantics to handle network variability. Ultimately, these steps aim to establish a unified, verifiable low-code foundation for dependable orchestration across cyber-physical domains.

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